

Investigation of magnetic properties of a cluster-glass system Dy₅PdNi

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Abstract

Rare earth intermetallic compounds of the form R₅Pd₂ are extensively investigated as these materials have complex magnetic behavior [1-2]. Dy₅Pd₂ belongs to this family and exhibits glassy magnetic state along with magnetocaloric effect (MCE) [2]. Ni substitution at the Pd site can be an effective approach to tune the magnetic properties of Dy₅Pd₂. Therefore, investigations were carried out on the compound Dy₅PdNi. DC magnetization shows a peak at 38 K and below this temperature glass-like magnetic behavior had been observed. Inverse susceptibility was fitted with Curie-Weiss law, which deviates from a straight line below 90 K indicating that the short range magnetic ordering persists up to 90 K. Dy₅PdNi exhibits irreversible behavior at ~ 38 K when measured under the zero field cooled (ZFC) and field cooled (FC) protocols. With increasing field, this irreversibility temperature is decreased indicating the presence of glass-like magnetic state. Heat capacity results do not show any sharp peak, which supports the absence of long range magnetic ordering in this compound. AC susceptibility measurements show a shift in peak temperature with frequency. Mydosh parameter ($\delta T_f = [\Delta T_f / (T_f \Delta \log f)]$), for this compound was found to be around 0.025. Such a value is noted for other compounds showing cluster glass behavior implying that the observed glassy phase in this compound is cluster glass-like. In this compound, both conventional and inverse MCE are observed. The maximum value of the magnetic entropy change for a field change of 70 kOe was around 8.85 J/kg-K (at 55K) which is significant, indicating that Dy₅PdNi can be a good magnetocaloric material.

Keywords: Intermetallic compounds, Rare earth metal and alloy, Magnetic materials and magnetocaloric effect.

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References

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